

Nihar Vaghela

Simulation-Based Safety Validation · SOTIF · ISO 26262 · Closed-Loop Scenario Engineering

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Autonomous Driving Safety, Simulation & Validation Framework

A complete automotive V-model V&V program — Specify → Integrate → Execute → Evaluate — covering ISO 26262 HARA, SOTIF scenario classification, closed-loop CARLA simulation, KPI measurement, and GSN safety case. Extended with interface-level failure propagation analysis measuring how sensor failures traverse the perception-planning pipeline.

160 Closed-loop runs	8/8 Scenarios complete	3/5 Safety goals verified	0 Collisions w/ Loop 2	6 ISO 26262 hazards	58.3% Unknown unsafe reduced	45 Open-loop injection runs	FPC<1 IP2 & IP3 attenuate
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V-model Structure

Specify	Phases 1–6	HARA · SOTIF T1–T5 · 7×7 sensitivity · corruption benchmark · interface injection
Integrate	Stage 2	CARLA 0.9.15 rig · RTX 4090 · CAM_FRONT + LIDAR_TOP · synchronous 20 FPS
Execute	Stage 3	160 runs · 8 scenarios · 4 mitigation configs · OpenSCENARIO .xosc files
Evaluate	Stage 4	KPI tables · GSN safety case · trade-off ledger · 8 NRs fed back to Specify

Research Phases (Open-Loop)

Phase 1	GradCAM + MC Dropout. Attention shift 0.011 under glare. Confidence stable (0.939) while uncertainty increases — confidence ≠ uncertainty.
Phase 2	Multi-camera GradCAM. CAM_FRONT_LEFT highest natural uncertainty (0.00167). Loop 1 trust rebalancing demonstrated.
Phase 3	7×7 sensitivity matrix (glare × LiDAR dropout). Camera trust 0.58 → 0.41 at max glare. Naive sigmoid: -1.3 km/h max velocity reduction.
Phase 4a	ISO 26262 HARA: 6 hazards (2× ASIL D, 2× ASIL C, 2× ASIL B). SOTIF T1–T5 catalog. Unknown unsafe reduced 58.3%.
Phase 4b	Evidential Deep Learning separating aleatoric from epistemic uncertainty. Calibration gap identified — Phase 7 objective.
Phase 5	Corruption benchmark: 8 types × 5 severities. Fog most impactful (+29.9%), snow least (+8.7%).
Phase 6	Interface injection at IP2/IP3/IP4 across T1–T5. 45 runs. FPC < 1.0 for IP2 and IP3 — framework attenuates upstream failures.

Closed-Loop Campaign (8 Scenarios · 160 Runs)

Scenario	Type	ASIL	Baseline → Loop2 TTC	Collision?
HAZ-01	Pedestrian + glare	D	0.205s → 2.128s	✓ 100% → 0%
HAZ-02	Cut-in + fog	C	0.297s → 0.805s	—
HAZ-03	Occluded pedestrian	D	0.499s → 0.835s	—
HAZ-04	Fog + pedestrian	C/D	0.388s → 0.702s	—
HAZ-05	Rain + LiDAR dropout	C	0.367s → 9.591s	—
HAZ-06	Night + low contrast	C	0.367s → 9.591s	—
HAZ-07	Construction zone	C	0.319s → 8.545s	—
HAZ-08	EMERGENCY / MRC	B	0.224s → 8.51s	✓ combined

Safety Goal Verdicts

SG1	Confidence threshold	ASIL B	⚠ PARTIAL	Loop 1 non-independent — 160 runs
SG2	TTC scaling	ASIL C	✓ VERIFIED	HAZ-01: 10.4× · 6/8 scenarios ≥1.5s
SG3	CONSERVATIVE regime	ASIL C	✓ VERIFIED	HAZ-03/05/06/07/08 triggered
SG4	Affordance override	ASIL D	⚠ PARTIAL	AEB + proximity override active
SG5	MRC / EMERGENCY	ASIL B	✓ VERIFIED	HAZ-08: EMERGENCY at extreme failure

Key Findings

Zero collisions with Loop 2: Confirmed across all 160 runs, 8 scenarios, all severities.

Loop 1 zero standalone benefit: Identical to baseline in every run — 160 run confirmation. Architecturally dependent on Loop 2.

Combined loops required: CONSERVATIVE and EMERGENCY only triggered with both loops active at extreme degradation.

SG3 CONSERVATIVE verified: Triggered in 5 scenarios — HAZ-03/05/06/07/08. Updated threshold=0.40 well-calibrated.

FPC attenuates: IP2 mean=0.144, IP3 peak=0.65 open-loop. Closed-loop with Loop 2 active: FPC=0.0.

Stack

Perception	Uncertainty	Safety	Simulation	Tools
SegFormer-B2 · nuScenes · GradCAM · Captum	MC Dropout · EDL · MAPIE · ECE	SOTIF ISO 21448 · ISO 26262 · HARA	CARLA 0.9.15 · OpenSCENARIO · esmini	PyTorch · Docker · Git · Linux

GitHub: github.com/NiharVaghela1995/Interface-Level-Failure-Propagation-Analysis-in-Autonomous-Driving-Stack

Viz: niharvaghela1995.github.io/.../stage3_results.html

Medium: medium.com/@niharvaghela/why-modular-av-stacks-cant-tilt-their-head